

SOCIALIZATION THROUGH SPORT

Mir Sharif Hasanⁱ

Student Counselor (Sport),
North Bengal International University,
Rajshahi, Bangladesh

Abstract:

Sport as a social tool can undeniably provide a powerful platform to promote sports and physical activities and gender equality. Sport cannot solve all the unwanted social problems but however it has provided itself to be a valuable & powerful tool to build bridges, cross borders and social cohesion. Sports and active social activities of the Olympic movement that are related to using sport to improve physical activities in the population, giving access to sport as a right for all and on engaging in sport activities with special focus on youth. Olympic agenda ever reflects the fact that sport is more important for an active life style in society and enhancing activities which should be a key goal of all governmental & non-governmental agencies throughout the world.

Keywords: sport & active society, Olympic movement, sport as a right for all citizens, active life style in the society, powerful platform to promote gender equality

1. Introduction

The development of personality of a citizen is both the goal and the complete accomplishment of society. The main desire of social institution is the improvement of the opportunities of the mass working people and their spouse for their good abilities to make education, culture and sport.

The development of physical culture and sport become a real need felt very much on eve of inception of modern society. Every individual has an important social task which must be systematically carried out and together with Sportsmen, trainers, administrators and social organizations.

All citizens shall be able to have optimum joy of life and maintain his or her health and engagement in regular active recreation through continuous encouragement of sports. The quality of sport facilities shall be improved through systematic maintenance, reconstruction and modernizations in keeping with local sports socialisation centres.

ⁱ Correspondence: email mirsharif47@yahoo.com

New facilities shall be planned and expand to accumulate more people in sport. It should be recorded that how many people are taking part in sport activities annually which sponsored and look after by the community centres. The sponsored such programme has to develop both health and pleasure and to give leisure time more meaningful. The most effective form of sports activities is the regular training and participation in mass sports competitions. An active initiative should be given regarding cultural and sports life of the young people of our society.

Sport is a unified sequence of movement by physical and mental action. This an activity, which is performed by one's own, will as a form of sport. No one should be forced to participate in sport. It should be promoted as an enjoyable activity, which builds skills, confidence knowledge of game and friendships. Sports are exciting and fun when the barriers to enjoyment have been removed.

2. Application of Social Behavior and Norms

Playing sports with equipment appropriately modified to individual physical capabilities enables participants to be involved without risk of injury or humiliation. Modified rules allow development of skills by giving emphasis on whatever abilities the participant possesses. Each participant is quite able to work towards developing his or her potential.

One of the benefits of modified sport is that activities are not identified as being predominantly male or female. The same is played on equal basis. Sport to cater to each individuals physical, intellectual and emotional level of development. In all structure of society, the level of sports activities will also be raised to the maximum possible to meet new needs. This means that sport will be made available to all citizens, that the Potential individual will be given all possible encouragement, and that sport games will be used for the creation of a general developed, well balanced personality and for recreation. This will also be an important contribution to human society in so far as it does part of the job of making life better, and all groups of people happier.

Based on the need of a society for sport activities, laws and the system may be determined by the state policy that the state and social organizations responsible for working closely together for making sport available to everyone. The Constitution of the state should be made in such a way that the right of all citizens to physical education and the necessary responsibilities of state performed accordingly. Modern society would have to serve the general physical and mental improvement of her people. A big task is planned on long-range basis so that step by step the whole population will become involved. The physical culture will be programmed in all social and vocational institutions that no one is neglected.

Regular sports activities may be included in course curriculum in nursery school, kindergartens, schools, vocational school and colleges several times a week for the young generation as a part of leisure time activity.

For mass people conditions for sport must be improved so that they can participate in the residential areas, nationally owned enterprise, cooperative farms, and recreational centres.

All sports, controlling authorities of the countries should be given tasks of winning ever more young people and adults to more active form of sports and also encourage exercise; training and competitions in different kinds of sports. Other social and political organisations should also have the responsibilities to create sports programmes.

Government organizations such as the ministries of education, health, national defence and especially the ministry of youth and sports all in cooperation with the sport controlling authorities of the countries have the responsibility of assisting the sports efforts and to develop new initiatives themselves.

Government organizations and particularly top sports controlling authority should take initiative and organize sports for working people of the country. This will result in an increase in membership and guidance of these members needed sufficient volunteer trainers. There should be some competent physical culture colleges in the country who will be responsible for the training and education of volunteer trainers, judges and referees along with other education of the country.

The youth movement with the ministry of sports and culture and other pioneer organization is the most effective method to create enthusiasm among the whole younger generation of a country and to explore them as a positive force for nation building. On the other hand, working people's participation in physical culture activities make themselves healthy and stronger so it is possible by them for working actively to produce the material goods satisfactorily and it will be a big material gain indeed. The society and its component institutions should be a concern of the masses. Sport and the Society have a significant relationship, which can form a stronger development based in industrialized nation. The society nourished many-sided talency, which is socially and politically determined for the well-being of human.

3. Conclusion

With the development of human physical performances, we should bring it in our mind the Pierre de Coubertin's social reconstruction philosophy for a peaceful prosperous world. Human being is socially oriented so every human quality develops initially from this stage and goes to the future so we should look after to build a welfare society for best exploitation of all advantages. We acknowledge ourselves to the Olympic ideals, which is inseparably linked with the worldwide struggle for peace and understanding between nations.

References

1. David Rowe (2016). Why sport needs sociology and why sociology needs sports. Retrieved from <https://idrottsforum.org/forumbloggen/why-sport-needs-sociology-and-why-sociology-needs-sport/>
2. Birrell, Susan (1988). Discourses on the gender/sport relationship from women in part of gender relations, "exercise and sport sciences review 16: 459 – 502.

3. Bourdieu, Pierre (1978). "Sports & Social class" *Social science information* 7: 819 – 40.
4. Coakley, Jay (1993). "Sport & Socialisation," *Exercise & sport sciences Reviews*, 21: 169 – 200.
5. Donnelly, Peter (2003). "Sport and Social theory, PP 11 – 27 in *sport & society*, edited by B. Houlihan, London, England Sage.

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